

IMI2 Project No 777372 - RESOLUTE

Research empowerment on solute carriers

WP8 – Knowledge integration and data management

D8.6 RESOLUTE web portal

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V0.4	30 Dec 2019	Minor changes from Thomas Brandl (CeMM)
V1.0	2 Jan 2020	Final Version

¹ Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² Public, fully open.

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Publishable Summary

Solute carrier (SLC) membrane transport proteins control essential physiological functions, including nutrient uptake, ion transport, and waste removal. SLCs can be seen as gatekeepers and include 446 membrane proteins arranged into 65 families. SLCs are the second-largest family of membrane proteins in the human genome and are vital for maintaining homeostasis in the body and in individual cells. RESOLUTE's ambitious aim is to assign biochemical and biological functions to as many SLC genes as possible using a systematic approach.

The RESOLUTE web portal is the gateway to RESOLUTE information and resources. Next to general information and news on the consortium and its partners, it provides an interface to the RESOLUTE knowledgebase and the RESOLUTE database.

Introduction

The RESOLUTE web portal serves as a major entry point to all information on and resources generated by the RESOLUTE consortium. It conveys our mission, introduces the consortium, provides the latest news, offers an option to subscribe for a newsletter, and provides an interface to the RESOLUTE data- and knowledgebase. Available scientific data are divided into 2 main sections: knowledgebase and database. The knowledgebase integrates publicly available data on members of SLC families and associated drugs and ligands. The RESOLUTE database is an experiment and dataset centric database of all results generated in the RESOLUTE project, representing the central point of data management, data curation and data access throughout the RESOLUTE project. This report summarizes the current state of the RESOLUTE web portal and its implementation.

Implementation

The hardware infrastructure for the RESOLUTE web portal is provided by the CeMM IT department. Employment of virtual machines allows for maximal flexibility and scalability. The RESOLUTE web portal represents the frontend to most of RESOLUTE's services. It is built on open-source software wherever possible and reasonable. Figure 1 shows a simplified summary of the overall architecture.

Figure 1. Overview on RESOLUTE's IT infrastructure and technology stack.

The RESOLUTE web portal is built on state-of-the-art web-engineering technologies. It is implemented in an open-source, component based web user interface framework (Vue.js) as a single-page application with a “thin server” backend architecture, meaning that the client runs most of the application logic and the backend is only requested for specific services such as authentication or data queries. The Apollo GraphQL client (open source) is used for communication to the server.

Compatibility

Adhering to state-of-the-art web standards (HTML5, ES6, CSS3), the frontend is compatible to all modern web browsers. We test compatibility with Mozilla Firefox (open source) and with Google Chrome. Compatibility to mobile devices will be a focus for improvement in future release cycles.

Security

Authentication for accessing non-public areas of the RESOLUTE web portal is provided by a Microsoft Azure Active Directory (via Office365), which is already employed by the consortium for communication and data sharing (see also Data Management Plan; deliverable 8.1). The authorization protocol implemented is based on OAuth2 to ensure only members of the RESOLUTE consortium having access.

Authenticated as well as unauthenticated (i.e. public) access to data and information in the RESOLUTE web portal, the RESOLUTE knowledgebase, and the RESOLUTE database will be protected by implementation of transport layer security using the secure communication protocol (HTTPS).

FAIR

The RESOLUTE web portal also has to support the efforts of data FAIRification in the RESOLUTE project. Quite some aspects dealing with findability and accessibility do not only affect the dataset itself but also the actual hosting solution. The web portal will implement a series of metadata features, i.a. by implementing the Bioschemas³ specification, ontologies and controlled vocabularies, to enable a high level of FAIRness.

Structure

The RESOLUTE web portal features a top-level menu providing access to multiple sections:

Sections About, Consortium, Solute Carriers, Facts and Figures

These sections aim to introduce to the variety of visitors the RESOLUTE project and consortium. All partners are presented, solute carriers are described and RESOLUTE's scope and aim is announced.

³ <http://bioschemas.org>

Figure 2. “About” section in the RESOLUTE web portal.

Section News

The news section contains public information and announcements on events related to the RESOLUTE consortium. This content can be also subscribed to by signing up for the RESOLUTE newsletter. A simple CMS allows a restricted group of authors for page and news editing.

Figure 3. “News” section in the RESOLUTE web portal.

Sections Knowledgebase & Database

The web portal includes a web interface to the RESOLUTE database (see also Deliverable D8.6) and the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (see also Deliverable D8.5). Both sources expose an API which the web portal provides a graphical user interface for. For open-access datasets, the RESOLUTE web portal provides access without the need for authentication or specialized software (apart from a standards-compliant modern web browser). For accessing unpublished datasets, an authorization step is required (see Implementation).

The RESOLUTE database has metadata and data on reagents, samples, experiments, and results. The web portal provides public, open access to all published items of the RESOLUTE database. Datasets can be downloaded directly from the web portal, or via a link to another, domain-specific data repository.

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase is a compilation of publicly available knowledge, information and resources on the Solute Carrier gene family and all of its members. Moreover, it also integrates the analysed and interpreted datasets created from the RESOLUTE project. Using the web portal, one can explore the knowledgebase and search for a specific SLC directly from within the web browser.

Figure 4. “Database” section in the RESOLUTE web portal.

Sections Links and Contact

Additional and related information to SLCs is provided in the Links section and in the Contact section key consortium members are highlighted to help finding the right contact person.

Figure 5. “Contact” section in the RESOLUTE web portal.

Data sharing and approval process

The internal procedure for disseminating results was established within the RESOLUTE consortium to ensure the high quality and value of the results and reagents. The details of the procedure are described in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D9.2) and Data Management Plan (D8.1). Briefly, data (or reagent) release proposals are prepared by data owner(s) and presented during one of the data annotation and release workshop. At the workshop, the proposals will be discussed in detail with the aim of curating data, extending and refining annotation and strengthening quality control. Within a week after the workshop, the proposals are forwarded to the publication and dissemination officers of all consortium partners. In case there are no objections within a 30 days review period, the data will be published and openly accessible in the RESOLUTE database and corresponding public databases.

To notify the scientific community about newly released data and reagents from RESOLUTE, news are published on the web-portal as well as featured in the external newsletter (3-4 times per year).

Dissemination

The RESOLUTE web portal is accessible at the following URI:

<https://re-solute.eu/>

Sustainability

CeMM commits to support and maintain the RESOLUTE web portal during the whole period of RESOLUTE and 5 years after end of the grant, i.e. until mid of 2028.

Appendix

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content management system
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
DAL	Data Access Layer
ES6	ECMAScript 6
FAIR	a set of guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
RESOLUTE	Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers
SLC	Solute Carrier
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier